

A STUDY ON ANALYTICAL REPORT RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION PROCESS IN ASGARDIA CORP, CHENNAI

K. Abinaya*, P. T. J. K. Lilian & Dr. B. Velmurugan*****

* II Year MBA, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Natham, Dindigul, Tamil Nadu

** Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering and Technology, Natham, Dindigul, Tamil Nadu

*** Professor & Head, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering and Technology, Natham, Dindigul, Tamil Nadu

Cite This Article: K. Abinaya, P. T. J. K. Lilian & Dr. B. Velmurugan, "A Study on Analytical Report Recruitment and Selection Process in Asgardia Corp, Chennai", *International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research*, Volume 9, Issue 2, July - December, Page Number 35-39, 2024.

Copy Right: © DV Publication, 2024 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Better recruitment and selection strategies result in improved organizational outcomes. Recruitment is the process of searching for prospective employees and stimulating them to apply for jobs in the organization. Selection may be defined as the process by which the organization chooses from among the applicants, those people whom they feel would best meet the job requirement, considering current environmental condition. In today's Competitive business environment, organizations have to respond to the requirements for people. It is important for an organization adopt well structured recruitment policy, which can be implemented effectively to get the best results. This study helps the organization to identify the area of problem and suggest way to improve the recruitment and selection process, this study focus on understanding recruitment and selection process. Convenient sampling is used in this study. The sample size for the study is 80. The tools that are used in this study are Percentage analysis and Chi square test is used.

Key Words: Recruitment, Selection, Employee.

Introduction:

Acquiring and retaining high-quality talent is critical to an organization's success. As the job market becomes increasingly competitive and the available skills grow more diverse, recruiter need to be more selective in their choices, since poor recruiting decisions can produce long-term negative effects, among them high training and development costs to minimize the incidence of poor performance and high turnover which, in turn, impact staff morale, the production of high quality goods and services and there tension of organizational memory. At worst, the organization can fail to achieve its objectives there by losing its competitive edge and its share of the market Human resource department plays a crucial role in this process. The backbone of any successful company is the HR department, and without a talented group of people to hire, culture, and inform employees, the company is doomed for failure. Human resource is most valuable assets in the organization. Profitability of the organization depends on its utilization. If there utilization is done properly will make profit otherwise it will make loss. To procure right man at right place in right time, some information regarding job and job doer is highly essential.

Factors Affecting Recruitment:

- The size of the organization
- The Employment conditions in the community where the organization is located.
- The effects of past recruiting efforts which show the organization's ability to location retain the good performing people.
- Working conditions, salary and benefit packages offered by the organization.
- The future expansion and production programs.

Factors Types:

- Internal factors
- External factors

Internal Factors:

- Recruitment policy of the organization
- Human resource planning strategy of the company
- Size of the organization and number of people employed
- Cost involved in recruiting employees
- Growth and expansion plans of the organization
- Company pay package
- Career planning and growth
- Quality of work life
- Role of trade union

External Factors:

- Supply and demand of specific skills in the labor market.
- Political and legal factors like reservations of jobs for specific sections of society etc.
- The job seekers image perception of the company.
- Information system like employment exchange/ tele recruitment like internet.
- Labor market condition

Sources of Recruitment:

Internal Sources:

The most common internal sources of internal recruitment are

- Personal recommendations
- Notice boards
- Newsletters
- Memoranda

External Sources:

There are many sources to choose from if you are seeking to recruit from outside the company.

- Word of mouth
- Notices
- Job centers
- Private agencies and consultants
- Education institutions
- Radio
- Television

Statement of the Problem:

“A Study on Recruiting and Selection” A solid recruitment and selection process can help convince top management candidates that reduces turnover and absenteeism and selection process improve the employee engagement and my study on recruiting and selection in ASGARDIA CORP give me to scope to know in detail about the different techniques and method adopted by ASGARDIA CORP to train their employees very effectively. In many problems regarding their employees that recruiting and selection process are fail to hiring the employees for their organization and they are not bring any progress with themselves and not stay longer in their organization. Rapidly hiring practice is very costly.

Objectives of the Study:

To get right person at right place and in right time, the organization should have the specific and clear policies and recruitment and selection methods which are essential for the growth of the organization.

- To analyze the process of recruiting and selection of the candidates.
- To observe the procedure involved in selecting the candidates.
- To study the employee satisfactory level with the existing recruitment polices.
- To analyze the consequences of the recruitment and selection process
- To find out the problems and identifies the reason behind with recruiting procedure.

Need of the Study:

Selecting the right employee is an important goal for the recruitment team and establishing the correct process can enhance the experience of the Candidate, Interviewer, Hiring Manager and the HR Department. It can also help increase the effectiveness of your business.

- The study enables the company use all the recruitment strategies effectually in an organization
- To increase the effectiveness of different sources source for all types job in an organization.
- To obtain the employee that can be solved in order to help organizational goals.
- The study of the project is important which is need for recruiting and selection procedure followed by the organization
- To identify the company recruited efficient & qualitative candidates in an organization.

Scope of the Study:

To study the recruitment & Selection process will make the organization to a do a continuous improvement in recruitment & Selection process. This will provide the scope for further studies, to be conducted for betterment in these respected areas. This study can be used to measure the satisfaction level of recruitment & Selection Process. This is study will be useful to find out the different sources & techniques used in the recruitment and selection procedure The Company understands effectives sources in recruitment & selection procedure. This study will be useful to interview and test short listing candidates. This study can be used as a base for further research in this area.

Hypothesis of the Study:

It means tentative generalization of the validity of which remains the tested. In short it deals with certain assumptions made in the study.

Null Hypothesis:

A hypothesis which assumes that there is significant difference between sample statistics and population parameter is called null hypothesis. It is denoted by H_0

Alternative Hypothesis:

A hypothesis which assumes that there is significant difference between sample statistics and population parameter is called alternative hypothesis. It is denoted by H_1

Research Design:

The research design used in this project is descriptive in nature. The descriptive research is study in an attempt to obtain all relevant and accurate descriptive of the situation. A descriptive study is designed to describe details of the problem. Descriptive research includes surveys and fact findings enquiries of different kinds.

Research Methodology:

The research was done in order to understand the Recruitment and Selection Process followed at Asgardia Corp and the perception of the employees from all the cadres regarding it. In order to get the right kind of people in right place in the right time

the organization should have the specific and clear personnel, policies and recruitment methods which are essential for the growth of the organization. Hence it was necessary to conduct a research on the process.

Analytically Tools for the Study:

- Percentage analysis test
- Chi-square test
- Correlation

Limitations of the Study:

- The study is limited to the information given by the employees.
- Meeting some of the top management associates in the senior cadre was difficult.
- The study has been limited due to time constraint.
- There may be chances for the bias.

Company Profile:

Asgardia Corp grew into a trustworthy company with an impeccable record of deliverance. Asgardia imparts services related to Digital Marketing - Web Design/Development, SEO / SEM, SMO / SMM & PPC / Ads. Asgardia’s expertise is unchallenged towards complete customer satisfaction. ASGARDIA has an impeccable record of performance in the Indian States & Other parts of the world like the UK, USA, Australia, Singapore, Malaysia &, etc.,. We serve in all parts of the world by online support & ASGARDIA’s vision of tomorrow is exhilarating. The team is vigilant towards the vibrant changes and modernization. We’re a full-service creative digital agency in Chennai and we can help your business grow. We specializes in creating engaging digital experiences, including website design, branding, digital marketing and more. Asgardia Corp is committed to protecting your personal data and respecting your privacy and your rights, and this statement is intended to provide you with information on how your personal data is processed

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Screening Process of Candidates of the Respondents:

HR Consultant Process of the Respondent:

Recruitment Process to Maintain Vacancy of the Respondents:

Interviews from Different Departments of the Respondents:

Findings of the Study:

- Based on my study table, the majority 31.25% of respondents are 40-50 years old by their age.
- Based on my study table, the majority 87.5% of respondents are male in their organization
- Based on my study table, the majority 43.75% respondent are post graduate
- Based on the study table, the majority 37.5% respondents are 1 to 5 years' experience in their company.
- Based on my study table, the majority 31.25% respondents income level is 10000-25000
- Based on my study table, the majority 50% respondents are social media vacancies
- Based on my study table, the majority 56.25% respondents are no specification candidates
- Based on my study table, the majority 37.5% respondents are a free with fitness test for employees
- Based on my study table, the majority 50% respondents are strongly agree with screening process of candidates
- Based on my study table, the majority 68,75% respondents say no with hr team consultant process
- Based on my study table, the majority 62.5% of respondents say yes for training program is beneficial.
- Based on my study table, the majority of 75% respondents are internal employee
- Based on my table, the majority 31.25% of respondent are strongly agree in recruiting process to maintain the vacancy
- Based on my study table, the majority 70% of respondents are yes in different form of interviews.
- Based on my study table, the majority 44% of respondent say strongly agree in recruiting policy
- Based on my study table, the majority 31.25 % of respondents are satisfactory in recruiting and selection
- Based on my study table, the majority 30% of respondents are opportunities for attraction for apply job in Asgardia Corp
- Based on my study table, the majority 35% of respondents says external source for recruiting
- Based on my study table, the majority 31.25 % of respondents say yes group discussion

- Based on my study table, the majority 30% of respondents says qualification and experience
- Based on my study table, the majority 40% of respondents says two weeks' time taken for respondents.
- Based on my study table, the majority 30% informal and unstructured interviews

Suggestions:

- Organization should take some actions to develop their technology.
- The management should provide training program to the initial Level of employees when a new technology is implementing in the market.
- The recruitment and selection through placement agencies as the last resort and is utilized only when need.
- The recruitment and selection procedure should not to lengthy and time consuming.
- The candidates called for interview should be allotted timings and it should not overlap with each other.

Conclusion:

This presents the summary of the study and survey done in relation to the Recruitment and Selection in Asgardia Corp. The conclusion is drawn from the study and survey of the Company regarding the Recruitment and Selection process carried out there. The recruitment Process at Asgardia Corp to some extent is done objectively and therefore lot of bias hampers the future of the employees. Most of the employees were satisfied but changes are required according to the changing scenario as recruitment process has a great impact on the Working of the company as a fresh blood, new idea enters in the company. Selection process is good but it should also be modified according to the requirements and should job profile so that Main objective of selecting the candidate could be achieved.

References:

1. C.R. Kothari, "Research Methodology Methods and Techniques", Second Edition, New Age International Publishers, 2004.
2. Adriana Ribeiro "Recruiting and selection in a diverse workplace" Publisher Lap Lambert Academic Publishing, Germany, 26 June2010
3. Gareth Roberts "Recruiting and selection", Publishing Chartered Institute of Personnel & Development; 2nd edition (June1, 2005)
4. Islam Md Shajedul, Ahsan Md Ali "Recruitment and Selection Process of Prime Bank Limited"
5. Nivethigha, R. P., S. Divyabharathi, and B. Velmurugan. "Business ethics, values and social responsibility to an entrepreneur." International Journal of Research in Management & Business Studies 4.1 (2017): 18-21.
6. Murugeswari, S., S. Jambulingam, B. Velmurugan, and K. Binith Muthukrishnan. "Challenges of Women Leaders and Managerial Effectiveness in It Industry in Coimbatore." Ann. For. Res 65, no. 1 (2022): 6725-6731.
7. Velmurugan, B., et al. "AI Insights Deciphering India's Ascendancy Through the Digital Library: Navigating the Digital Realm India's Odyssey Towards Information Equity and Technological Eminence." Improving Library Systems with AI: Applications, Approaches, and Bibliometric Insights. IGI Global, 2024. 285-293.
8. Sangeetha, Ms M., Mrs V. Tamilselvi, and B. Velmurugan. "A Study on Employee Absenteeism: Study at Sri Vinayaga Containers, Dindigul." (2023).
9. Agussalim, M., Ayu Rezkiana Putri, M., & Ali, H. (2018). Analysis work discipline and work spirit toward performance of employees (case study tax office Pratama two Padang). International Journal of Economic Research.